

Guidelines for PROBE community in Zenodo

Introduction

Over the duration of the PROBE Cost action, its members have accumulated many documents. This includes deliverables of the action, reports, scientific publications, standard operating procedures, tools, software, etc. Any member, user, and stakeholder of the PROBE community should be able to easily find relevant information after the action has ended. Documents uploaded and published on Zenodo are stored safely, openly accessible, citable, and traceable. A Zenodo repository was thus created as a sustainable archive of the wealth of knowledge and expertise gathered during the PROBE Cost action.

An extensive list of keywords is used to label all files uploaded to the repository. Other meta data include author/creator, contributors, description/abstract, and funding.

This document includes guidelines on how to upload a contribution, as well as an overview on how to find relevant information within the PROBE community space on Zenodo.

Document upload

Step 1: Sign up for Zenodo

- Sign up at <https://zenodo.org/>
- Put your Zenodo user name [in this google form](#). We can then add you to the PROBE community.

Step 2: Upload your document

- *Please do not upload documents/publications that already have a DOI!*
- Find the PROBE community here: <https://zenodo.org/communities/probe-cost>
- Go there and click “New Upload”

2 results found Sort by Newest

Versions

March 18, 2024 (version 1.0) Report Open

View all versions

Access status

Open 1

Restricted 1

Report on cloud radar survey at a European level
Acquistapace, Claudia

To create a knowledge base on the current status of the cloud radars operating in the EU, the PROBE COST ACTION completed a survey (<https://forms.gle/kVMCbFQ5BTQD1d7C6>) to understand the current state of the cloud radars operating in European countries, investigate the needs of the operators and put them in contact. We retrieved information on t...

Uploaded on March 18, 2024 4 3

- Upload your pdf.
- Fill in as many fields as possible, as detailed as possible.
 - Add a DOI
 - *Creator* is the main author of the contribution. More than one *Creator* can be added. Do this for all co-authors. Only *Creators* will appear in the DOI citation.

Description

Paragraph B I

+ Add description

- Zenodo seems to have difficulties finding people at the stage of *Creators* and *Contributors*. If you cannot find people by their ID or Zenodo user name, you need to complete the form yourself. Do this as detailed as possible for each person.

Add contributor

Person Organization

Search for persons by name, identifier, or affiliation...

Family name

Family name

Given names

Given names

Identifiers

e.g. ORCID, ISNI or GND.

Affiliations

Search or create affiliation

Role *

Select role

✕ Cancel

✓ Save and add another

✓ Save

- Although it is not a mandatory field, please include a *Description* to help with the approval process (see step 4 in this document). It should include an abstract/short summary of your work. This is necessary for the repository managers to judge if the selected *Keywords* match the content of the entry.
- Add all *Keywords* that apply. Refer to the list of keywords in the table below (to update with final version). This is an important step to make sure your work will be found and remains useful to the community and external users.
- Always use *Keyword* “PROBE COST action”.

Key words by deliverable	Key words by instrument	Keywords for operation and processing	Key words by product	Key words by network	Key words by document type
PROBE COST action (for all items!)	Automatic lidar (ALC)	Operation guidelines	Clouds	ACTRIS	VMG full report
Stakeholders (D1.1, D1.3)	Ceilometer (ALC)	Uncertainty	Precipitation	E-Profile	VMG short report
User requirements (D1.2)	ALC (automatic lidar and ceilometer)	Calibration	Wind	GRUAN	VMG abstract
Network requirements (D3.2)	Doppler lidar	Overlap correction	Turbulence	ICOS	Joint network document
Impact (D1.5)	Doppler cloud radar	Scanning strategy	Mixing	ARM	Joint network document section
ABL parameters (D2.1)	Microwave radiometer	Wind retrieval	Vertical velocity variance	Urban network	Standard operating procedure
Review paper (D2.1)	MWR	Turbulence	Eddy dissipation	Meso-scale	SOP

		retrieval	rate	network	
Scientific publication (publication in peer reviewed journal, D2.2)	Uncrewed aerial systems (UAS)	DBS	TKE	National network	
Instrument synergy (D2.2)	Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV)	VAD	Gust	Network	
Data assimilation (D2.3)	lidar	Vertical stare	Wind shear	RI-URBANS	
Re-analysis (D2.3)	radar	Background	Low level jet	ICOS-Cities	
Data standard (D3.1)	W-band radar	Background correction	Alert	Network design	
Format standard (D3.1)	Ka-band radar		Temperature	CCRES	
Software tools (D3.3)			Humidity		
Instrument configuration (D4.1)			Inversion		
Instrument operation (D4.1)			Forecast indices		
Instrument calibration (D4.1)			Fog		
Instrument field test (D4.3)			Icing		
Campaign (D4.3)			Aerosols		
Quality control (D4.1)			Depolarisation		
Data product (level 1 and level 2, D4.2)			Volcanic ash		
Dissemination			Pollen		
D1.1			Forest fires		
D1.2			Air quality		
D1.3			ABL characterisation (duplicate from ABL parameters?)		
D1.4			ABL height		
D1.5			Boundary layer height		
D2.1			Mixed-layer height		
D2.2			MLH		
D2.3			Atmospheric stability		
D3.1			Richardson number		
D3.2			Synergy		
D3.3			Elevated layers		
D4.1			Entrainment		
D4.2			Backscatter		
D4.3					

- Add VMG/STSM (or other) funding, where applicable.

Funding
▼

 Awards

 Virtual mobility grant E-COST-GRANT-CA18235-ebed9be5

European Cooperation in Science and Technology

Edit
Remove

+ Add award

+ Add custom

- For VM/STSM grant use “Add custom”. You find your grant number in the grant letter from the e-cost system.

Add custom award

Funder*

European Cooperation in Science and Technology ✕

Award information (optional)

Number	Title	URL
E-COST-GRANT-CA18235-yournumt	Virtual mobility grant	Award URL

✕ Cancel ✓ Add award

Step 3: Publish your document

- During the upload procedure you can save the repository entry as draft any time.
- When you are done, select either “public” or “restricted” visibility and click “Submit for Review”.

Draft ⓘ

Visibility*

Files only

Public Restricted

 Public
The record and files are publicly accessible.

Options

Apply an embargo ⓘ
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

- If you decide on “Restricted” visibility, please justify in the “Message to curators” field.

Submit for review

⚠ Before requesting review, please read and check the following:

The 'PROBE' curators will have access to view and edit your upload's metadata and files.

If your upload is accepted by the community curators, it will be immediately published. Before that, you will still be able to modify metadata and files of this upload.

Message to curators (optional)

CancelSubmit record for review

Step 4: Review and approval

- Your entry will be reviewed by managers or curators of the PROBE community.
- They will check:
 - choice of document type,
 - existence of description,
 - consistency of keywords,
 - COST funding acknowledgement for VMG and STSM reports,
 - justification of “restricted” access.
- Once the entry is approved, it is added to the PROBE community and a DOI is assigned to it.

DOI assignment and version control

Upon first upload of an entry, you'll receive two DOI. One DOI is for the first version of the new upload. The second DOI represents all versions and will always link to the latest version. When you update your entry (document or meta data), you will receive another DOI for the new version. You can always use the DOI written in “Cite all versions?” to refer to the most recent version of your entry.

Versions

Version v2	Mar 26, 2024
10.5281/zenodo.10876278	
Version v1	Mar 25, 2024
10.5281/zenodo.10869518	

[View all 2 versions](#)

Cite all versions? You can cite all versions by using the DOI [10.5281/zenodo.10869517](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10869517). This DOI represents all versions, and will always resolve to the latest one. [Read more.](#)

Add existing Zenodo entry to PROBE community

For existing Zenodo entries that should be added to the PROBE community, go to the entry. There is a “Communities” panel on the right. Press the “Settings” symbol and select “Submit to community”. Find PROBE in the following Window (PROBE ideally should be under “My communities”). More detailed instructions [here](#).

Communities ⚙️

This record is not included

- + Submit to community
- 🗨 Pending submissions
- ⚙️ Manage communities

Details

Use the repository

Search and filter

All contributions to the community will be gathered in one Zenodo repository. There, one can select document type and/or keywords to filter for relevant topics. All uploads have been carefully revised for a consistent use of keywords to facilitate finding content.

In the [PROBE community on Zenodo](#), initially the full repository is displayed. Filter options can be found on the left panel. An incomplete example is shown below. To search for a specific topic, select the keywords of interest and get a list of relevant entries to the repository.

Versions

View all versions

Access status

- Open 1
- Restricted 1

Resource types

- > Publication 2

Subjects

- ACTRIS 1
- CCRES 1
- Data products 1
- Doppler lidar 1
- E-Profile 1
- Ka-band radar 1
- PROBE COST action 1
- Software tool 1
- Wind 1
- cloud radar 1

File type

- PDF 1